

PRIVAT Guidance Notes

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General guidance

The aim of PRIVAT is to support peer reviewers in evaluating the publishable quality of an in vitro experimental study manuscript. Because PRIVAT is structured, it will help an editor see what issues have or have not been covered by the reviewer comments, and therefore help the editor make a decision on a manuscript and/or recruit reviewers with any specific expertise necessary to complete the review.

PRIVAT is not a reporting standard or checklist, but an aid to manuscript evaluation and decision-making. It is intended to help a reviewer think; it does not do any thinking for a reviewer. It is therefore not expected that every reviewer will be able to answer every question. Indeed, part of the intended value of PRIVAT is identifying when a reviewer does not know an answer to a question because it is outside their expertise, as this helps the editor select an appropriately balanced panel for review.

It should also be noted that, as a general tool, not every question of PRIVAT will be equally important for every study. Reviewers are warmly encouraged to use their experience, expertise, and common sense in interpreting and answering any and all of the questions in PRIVAT.

Guidance on PRIVAT Questions

The following is not a comprehensive manual, as each question could fill a chapter of a textbook. Rather, we present brief pointers for interpreting the questions and explaining why they are part of PRIVAT.

1. Objectives and knowledge goals

Primary concerns: How well the study has articulated what it is seeking to find out and why it is being done, and avoiding the confirmatory fallacy (treating exploratory research as if it is hypothesis-testing).

- This short YouTube video ([link](#)) presents a short, simple overview of relevant ideas.

1.1 Concerns the objective of the study. The assumption is that experimental research will be hypothesis testing. However, much research is exploratory. If a study is exploratory, the knowledge goals of the study should still be made clear.

1.2 Concerns the justification for doing the study, in terms of its position in and contribution to the literature. Have the authors sufficiently explained why the study is being done? Is it worth doing? Etc.

1.3 Is about avoiding the confirmatory fallacy, whereby studies that are exploratory in nature may select specific findings post hoc and retrospectively present them as if they confirm a hypothesis.

2. Experimental set-up

Primary concerns: The broader issues around the suitability of the experimental design for delivering the objectives of the study. Expert judgement and experience are important for interpreting these general issues into the specific issues that may be presented by particular study designs.

2.1 Broadly concerns the experimental set-up. Lengthy comments may be necessary. Manuscripts often do not provide sufficiently detailed theoretical explanations of why their experimental set-up is suitable for the study objectives.

2.2 Concerns how good a model the experiment is of the target situation that is being modelled. This is often referred to as the “applicability” or “translatability” of a study. Limitations in applicability may be acceptable if suitably characterised, or a model may be completely inappropriate and misleading.

3. Power and replicates

Primary concern: whether there are enough biological replicates, and appropriate repeat tests of biological replicates, to provide a sufficiently precise or reliable measurement of the effect that changing the independent variables has on the outcomes (dependent variables) in the study.

In some study designs, where the exact same sample cannot be measured several times, it can be difficult to figure out what the biological samples are and if there are enough repeat measures. One way to think about this is in terms of the units of the study that could in theory be randomised. For example, a study may consist of 5 dose groups with three units in each group. The units within the dose group are the technical replicates. Each group of three

is the biological replicate as the groups of three could be randomised to the dose levels being administered.

This issue can be challenging to assess. Question 3.1 helps set up the answer to the remaining three questions 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4. Questions 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4 taken together help identify whether there is a risk of pseudoreplication (false inflation of sample size) that erroneously shrinks confidence intervals and p-values.

- The classic XKCD comic about [slope hypothesis tests](https://xkcd.com/2533/) (<https://xkcd.com/2533/>, reproduced below) illustrates several of the issues of interest in this domain.
- This introductory YouTube video ([link](#)) about power analysis presents a simple overview of the key concepts.

3.1 Involves checking that the experimental unit in the study has been correctly identified. This question helps set up the answer to the next three questions.

3.2 This is a check on the sufficiency of the number of experimental units to power the study, for example whether there are enough samples to test the hypothesis, given what is known about the expected effect size in the context of random variation in results.

3.3 This is a check on the sufficiency of the number of repeat tests on the same experimental unit, to help account for the impact of variations in experimental technique on the results of the study.

3.4 This is a check on whether the study has correctly differentiated between experimental units (biological replicates) and repeat tests on the same unit (technical replicates). If there are issues with 3.1-3.3, there are likely issues here as well.

4. Safeguards against systematic error (bias)

Primary concern: the measures that the study authors have taken to ensure their experimental procedures have not biased the results of their study.

Note that this is *not* a detailed risk of bias assessment: rather, it is a finite set of prompts to help a person engage with various bias issues during a peer-review process. If it is necessary to do a more complete check on validity, a tool specifically designed for this purpose should be used.

4.1 is a check on ensuring that each component of the test system is in fact what the authors think it is. This includes ensuring that e.g. impurities or errors in exposure level have not importantly impacted results, any cell lines have low enough rates of mutation that they will respond as they should, etc. What counts as an acceptably low level or rate, etc., may be challenging to judge.

4.2 is a check on systems calibration and investigator training, asking the reviewer to evaluate the extent to which they are satisfied that potential bias from misusing or inadequately maintaining equipment has been sufficiently minimised.

4.3 For some experimental designs, randomisation of the experimental unit to treatment group can be important. This question checks this issue in terms of whether the baseline characteristics of the experimental groups can be expected to be similar enough that randomisation becomes less important (e.g. if a cell culture is a homogeneous suspension, randomisation may matter less).

4.4 Investigator awareness of which experimental group that each individual experimental unit has been assigned can distort the results of a study, for example by resulting in differences in treatment of each unit, differences in interpretation of results (especially if measurements are subjective), and in other ways. Blinding can be difficult to achieve but may still be a limitation that should be made clear in a study.

4.5 Incomplete data (e.g. exclusion of outliers, data missing because experimental units failed, etc.) can distort the results of a study and thus needs to be handled appropriately.

5. Generation and reporting of results

Primary concern: the processes by which the authors have analysed their data to generate their results, and the decisions they have made about how to report their findings. The issues of interest in this domain cover how error might be introduced through analytical

processes and choices in what to report, the replicability of methods used, and appropriate adherence to any pre-planned methods.

5.1 Preregistration of the methods for collecting and analysing data helps prevent researchers from changing their methods in response to the data they are collecting. This increases the reliability of their results. Preregistration is currently rare in toxicology but worth checking on and encouraging.

5.2 Clear and consistent use of data visualisations, tables, etc. are an important part of a publication.

5.3 Because in vitro studies can generate a lot of data, it often needs to be cleaned and normalised before it is analysed. It is worth checking that the methods used for doing this are appropriate, in case they distort the results of the study.

5.4 Appropriate statistical assumptions and methods are an essential part of generating reliable results from study data.

5.5 Selective reporting can obviously distort the findings of a study. Without a protocol as reference (q5.1) it can be very difficult to determine if this is happening, but there might be indications (and sometimes it is obvious that authors only selected positive responses to report, for example.)

5.6 Sufficient raw data and code is important for third-party replication of results. How much is needed may not always be clear, and sometimes the journal will decide the policy on this, but as for other issues it is worth checking.

6. Interpretation of results into findings and conclusions

6.1 The need to account clearly for limitations should need no explaining. One nuance is that even a quite limited study, if its limitations and implications for future research are fully articulated, can still be worth publishing. Reviewers may wish to consider this.

6.2 Findings should reflect results and methods.

6.3 Similar to the theory for designing a study in a certain way, and explaining why the study was done, properly explaining what the findings of a study mean in the context of existing research can often be underdeveloped in study manuscripts.

7. Other issues relevant to publication

7.1 This can be a delicate issue, declarations are often not comprehensive, nor conflicts of interest well-understood by authors or journals. The journal [Evidence-Based Toxicology \(link to author guidance wiki\)](#) defines the issues as follows:

“A conflict of interest is any commitment, obligation, duty or goal associated with a particular social role or practice [...] Interests may be financial or non-financial in nature [...] Having an interest is not the same thing as having a conflict of interest [...] A conflict of interest arises when serving one interest could involve working at the expense of another interest [...] Conflicts of interest therefore need to be identified and managed in order to preserve the integrity of decision-making when doing research.”

7.2 Title and abstract should be an accurate summary of the main content of the study.

7.3 Study methods should be sufficiently detailed that the reader would have a reasonable chance of repeating the experimental approach. How much detail is needed can be challenging to judge.

7.4 In vitro methods can still require ethical approval. If it is needed, the approval process must be clearly described and appropriate to the study goals and materials.